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IMPACT OF GENDER IN THE USE OF THE MOST PREFERABLE VARIETY OF ENGLISH AMONG TERTIARY LEVEL LEARNERS IN LUCKNOW

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Abstract

Gender is a radical social factor and can be considered as an important independent variable in various disciplines of social research. Researches proved that gender differences make explicit impact on learners' academic interests, needs, and achievements (Halpern, 1986; Collins, Kenway and McLeod, 2000; Swiatek & Lupkowski-Shoplik, 2000). However, these researches have different claims on gender issue.

Use of language is an interesting field of investigation and has both academic and popular appeal. To study the impact of gender in use of language is the area of interest in this study. It is an effort to observe and to learn about the impact of gender in use of English language among tertiary level learners in Lucknow. This study intends to determine whether male and female are similar or different with respect to the use of the variety of English.

Keywords: *gender, social research, language use, etc.*

Introduction

Male and female are complementary of one another. It is completely unethical to grade them as superior and inferior. At the same time we cannot deny the fact that both differ from one another in terms of ability and capacity. At cultural level, there is no fundamental difference between male and female. Both learn the appropriate behaviors and attitudes from the family and overall culture they grow up with. At biological level, females and males differ fundamentally on physiological ground and their learning style. Both are endowed with their specific ability and capability. The existence of one without other is nothing more than an imagination. It is their process of socialisation that promotes the agenda of gender difference between them.

Language plays an important role in socialisation process. Language use is an intensive field of research and it plays a vital role to improve the prospects of both to be expressive and to be impressive. Baker (1992) gives a

detailed account of the variables that may affect the process of language use and attitude. The variables he talks about include age, gender, school, language ability, language background and cultural background (41-47). In this study gender is taken as an important independent variable. It aims to study the impact of gender in the use of the most preferable variety of English among tertiary level learners in Lucknow.

This study selected English language because it has a history of around more than 350 years in India; and has a very significant place on the communicative, linguistic, and cultural mosaic of India. It was introduced by Britishers as a tool of mental and linguistic colonisation which later on was used as a means of empowerment and emancipation. It is regarded as one of the most popular languages, learnt and taught all across the globe, and known as a language of power and prestige, of social mobility and progress. It is used as a link language to interconnect people from different cultural, communicative, and linguistic backgrounds.

It has huge number of varieties and sub-varieties having local tastes and tunes such as British English, American English, Australian English, New Zealand English, South African English, Indian English, etc. Its users can use any of the varieties as per their convenience but in written English, users are expected to follow the standard variety of American or British English. Various language groups wanted to learn and use English language for their economic betterment, either willingly or unwillingly.

During the conceptualization of this study, three varieties of English- British, American and Indian had been selected as source of reference. Later on, it was realised that Indian English is yet not codified and authenticated like American and British English. Therefore, in the present study, British and American varieties are used as a reference and Indian English is dropped.

Objective of the study

The objective of this study is twofold: first to observe the impact of gender in use of language and second to identify the variety of the English popular among the tertiary level learners in the city of Lucknow.

Hypothesis

In the socio-cultural and socio-linguistic scenario of Lucknow, it is observed that English is used in several intercultural and cross-cultural operations. In such a scenario, the following hypotheses are proposed in this study:

- British English is the most famous and preferred variety of English among the tertiary level learners of English in the city of Lucknow.
- Males are inclined towards British and females are towards American English.

Location and subject

Lucknow, the capital city of the state of Uttar Pradesh, is selected as a research location to carry out this study. It is also known for the *Nawabi* culture, *Ganga Yamuni Sabhyata*, its *Adab* and *Tihzeeb* (cultural refinement), legendary hospitality, world renowned cuisine, leisurely moods of life, and exquisite *Shane-e-Awadh*.

The subjects of this study are the tertiary level learners of various professional courses such as B.Tech, M.B.A., and M.C.A. etc. In contrast, the learners of English in various traditional courses such as in B.A. and M.A. study English from different perspectives and for different purpose. In traditional courses, English is taught as a core subject where learners study literature in English, and learn about history and mechanism of English. Unlike traditional learners, in professional courses; learners study English for specific purposes. English is taught to them as complementary subject to enhance their communicative ability in English. The area of this research interest is to explore the use of

English and to observe the perception of learners towards the use of English. Therefore, learners of tertiary level from various professional courses are selected as the subject.

Data collection tool and research design

A questionnaire cum evaluation sheet is used as a tool for data collection. It evaluates the learners’ preference between American and British equivalents. It contains three jumbled sets of American and British equivalent expressions, spellings and words. The learners are asked to select the most preferred option between the two that they use in their speech and writing. These sets seek to find out the learners’ inclination towards the most preferred variety of English.

Non-probability sample technique is used in this study where the convenience sampling technique is seasoned with the snowball sampling technique. In this study, data is collected from the learners of English at tertiary level in different technical and professional institutes in Lucknow as per the convenience. Subjects are further classified on the basis of gender into two categories- male and female.

Variable	Subdivision	Number	Total
Gender	Male	192	280
	Female	88	

Since access to the respondents is based on the availability of learners, the number of respondents is neither equal nor proportional. Section wise analysis has been made, and a subsequent interpretation has been done on the basis of majority rule.

Analysis and interpretation

Analysis and interpretation of section:

370 questionnaires were distributed to collect response from learners. Out of these, only 280 questionnaires are administered by learners and executed for analysis. Respondents are the student of various technical and professional courses as B.Tech, M.B.A., M.C.A., B.B.A., B.Com, B.J.M.C., etc. in various institutes of Lucknow. The respondents belong to the various parts of India as Madhya Pradesh (19), Bihar (33), Bengal (10), and Uttar Pradesh (218). 179 respondents belong to city of Lucknow. Rest of the respondents are non-native of Lucknow city, but they pursue technical and professional education in this city and contribute a significantly in the speech communities of Lucknow. Therefore, no matter where they belong to, all of them have been taken as a subject for this study. Out of 280, 192 are male and 88 are female respondents. Respondents belong to the age group 18 to 22.

In the analysis of the background section (Section: A) of the respondents, it is found that 72 (37.5%) males want to learn Indian English, 62 (32.29%) British English, 50 (26.04%) American English, and remaining 8 (4.16%) all these varieties. With respect to American and British English, it has been observed that equal number of females prefer American (32=36.36%) and British English (32=36.36%). 16 (18.18%) females want to learn Indian English while remaining 8 (9.09%) opt for ‘not sure’ in their reaction. 76 (39.58%) males prefer to use Indian English, 58 (30.20%) British English, 34 (17.70%) American English and the rest 24 (12.5%) are ‘not sure’. On the other hand, 40 (45.45%) females prefer to use Indian English, 38 (43.18%) British English and the remaining 10 (11.36%) opt for ‘not sure’.

Analysis and interpretation of section: B

To see the impact of structural preference in use of English, a series of expression of American and British equivalents are presented and respondents’ are asked to select the preferred structure among both.

	Variable	American	British	Both	None	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. deviation
Exp.:1	Male	138(71.9)	48(25)	4(2.1)	2(1)	1.7500	1	1	.50131
	Female	64(72.7)	18(20.5)	6(6.8)	(00)	1.8636	1	1	.50700
Exp.:2	Male	86(44.8)	104(54.2)	(00)	2(1)	1.4375	2	2	.51800
	Female	26(29.5)	62(70.5)	(00)	(00)	1.2955	2	2	.45886
Exp.:3	Male	78(40.6)	110(57.3)	2(1)	2(1)	1.5833	2	2	.53499
	Female	10(11.4)	78(88.6)	(00)	(00)	1.8864	2	2	.31919
Exp.:4	Male	48(25)	140(72.9)	2(1)	2(1)	1.2604	2	2	.48528
	Female	14(15.9)	74(84.1)	(00)	(00)	1.1591	2	2	.36786
Exp.:5	Male	78(40.6)	112(58.3)	(00)	2(1)	1.5729	2	2	.51663
	Female	46(52.3)	38(43.2)	4(4.5)	(00)	1.5227	1	1	.58678

Table 1: Statistical representation of the preferable expression in communication

- In the first set of expressions, similar median and mode values are observed. According to the mode values, both the counterparts prefer to use American expression.
- In the second set of expressions, corresponding median and mode values are recorded. As per the mode values, both the counterparts like to use British expression in comparison to American equivalent.
- In the third set of expressions, equivalent median and mode values are noticed. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer to use British expression.
- In the fourth set of expressions, even median and mode values are recorded. As per the mode values, the preferred expression of both the counterparts is British expression.
- In the fifth set of expressions, heterogeneous median and mode values are observed. As per the mode values, males prefer British while females prefer American equivalent.

In majority of cases both the counterparts inclined towards British expression. They prefer to use British structure of expression in their communication. It proves that gender as an independent variable that has no explicit impact in use of the preferable variety of language.

To see the impact of preference in written communication in English, a series of American and British spellings pairs are presented and respondents' were asked to select the preferred one.

- In the first set of spellings, dissimilar median and mode values are observed. As per the mode values, males prefer to use American spelling while females prefer to use British equivalent.
- In the second set of spellings, corresponding median and mode values are noticed. As per the mode values, the desired spelling in both the counterparts is British.
- In the third set of spellings, homogeneous median and mode values are observed. As per the mode values, both the counterparts like to use American spelling in comparison with British equivalent.
- In the fourth set of spellings, uniform median and mode values are obtained. As per the mode values, both the counterparts prefer to use British spelling
- In the fifth set of spellings, even median and mode values are acquired. As per the mode values, both counterparts inclined towards British spelling.
- In the sixth set of spellings, equivalent median and mode values are elicited. As per the mode values, the preferred spelling in both counterparts is British.
- In the seventh set of spellings, uniformity is noticed in both median and mode values. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer to use British spelling

	Variable	British	American	Both	None	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. deviation
Exp.:1	Male	80(41.7)	96(50)	16(8.3)	(00)	1.6667	2	2	.62524
	Female	44(50)	36(40.9)	8(9.1)	(00)	1.5909	1.5	1	.65454
Exp.:2	Male	128(66.7)	60(31.2)	4(2.1)	(00)	1.3542	1	1	.52136
	Female	50(56.8)	34(38.6)	4(4.5)	(00)	1.4773	1	1	.58678
Exp.:3	Male	86(44.8)	94(49)	12(6.2)	(00)	1.6146	2	2	.60313
	Female	38(43.2)	42(47.7)	8(9.1)	(00)	1.6136	2	2	.65094
Exp.:4	Male	100(52.1)	92(47.9)	(00)	(00)	1.5208	1	1	.50087
	Female	46(52.3)	42(47.7)	(00)	(00)	1.5227	1	1	.50235
Exp.:5	Male	168(87.5)	22(11.5)	2(1)	(00)	1.1354	1	1	.37234
	Female	84(95.5)	4(4.5)	(00)	(00)	1.0455	1	1	.20949
Exp.:6	Male	160(83.3)	30(15.6)	2(1)	(00)	1.1771	1	1	.40918
	Female	76(86.4)	10(11.4)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.1591	1	1	.42579
Exp.:7	Male	168(87.5)	14(7.3)	10(5.2)	(00)	1.9792	1	1	.35386
	Female	76(86.4)	8(9.1)	4(4.5)	(00)	1.9545	1	1	.36857
Exp.:8	Male	162(84.4)	28(14.6)	2(1)	(00)	1.1667	1	1	.40070
	Female	82(93.2)	6(6.8)	(00)	(00)	1.0682	1	1	.25350
Exp.:9	Male	184(95.8)	6(3.1)	2(1)	(00)	1.9792	1	1	.20359
	Female	84(95.5)	2(2.3)	2(2.3)	(00)	2.0000	1	1	.21442
Exp.:10	Male	156(81.2)	34(17.7)	2(1)	(00)	1.8333	1	1	.40070
	Female	76(86.4)	10(11.4)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.9091	1	1	.35996
Exp.:11	Male	170(88.5)	20(10.4)	2(1)	(00)	1.9062	1	1	.32611
	Female	80(90.9)	6(6.8)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.9545	1	1	.29977

Table 2: Statistical representation of the preferable spelling in writing

- In the eighth set of spellings, corresponding median and mode values are elicited. As per the mode values, both the counterparts incline towards British spelling.
- In the ninth set of spellings, even median and mode values are registered. As per the mode values, both the counterparts prefer to use British spelling.
- In the tenth set of spellings, similar median and mode values are noticed. As per the mode values, both counterparts inclined towards British spelling.
- In the eleventh set of spellings, equal median and mode values are drawn. As per the mode values, both the counterparts prefer to use British spelling.

In majority of cases, both the counterparts are inclined towards British spellings. They prefer to use British spelling in their written communication. Again, it reflects that in written communication gender has no significant impact on the use of English in terms of its varieties.

To see the impact of preference in speech, pairs of American and British equivalents are presented to know the respondents' preference.

- In the first set of expressions, similar median and mode values are observed. As per the mode values, both the counterparts prefer to use British expression.
- In the second set of expressions, homogeneous median and mode values are noticed. As per the mode values, both counterparts intend to American expression.
- In the third set of expressions, uniform median and mode values are recorded. As per the mode values, both counterparts incline towards American expression.

- In the fourth set of expressions, even median and mode values are obtained. As per the mode values, both counterparts are desired for American expression.
- In the fifth set of expressions, corresponding median and mode values are procured. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer British expression.
- In the sixth set of expressions, homogeneous median but heterogeneous mode values are observed. As per the mode values, equal number of males are inclined towards American and British expression while females are inclined towards British equivalent.
- In the seventh set of expressions, even median and mode values are elicited. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer American expression.
- In the eighth set of expressions, similar median and mode values are observed. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer British expression.

	Variable	British	American	Both	None	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. deviation
Exp.:1	Male	134(69.8)	46(24)	12(6.2)	(00)	1.8229	1	1	.52167
	Female	50(56.8)	24(27.3)	14(15.9)	(00)	1.8864	1	1	.65094
Exp.:2	Male	34(17.7)	150(78.1)	8(4.2)	(00)	1.8646	2	2	.44884
	Female	24(27.3)	62(70.5)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.7500	2	2	.48542
Exp.:3	Male	80(41.7)	108(56.2)	4(2.1)	(00)	1.6042	2	2	.53131
	Female	32(36.4)	54(61.4)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.6591	2	2	.52273
Exp.:4	Male	(00)	190(99)	2(1)	(00)	1.0208	2	2	.20359
	Female	(00)	86(97.7)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.0455	2	2	.29977
Exp.:5	Male	166(86.5)	16(8.3)	10(5.2)	(00)	1.9688	1	1	.36762
	Female	80(90.9)	6(6.8)	2(2.3)	(00)	1.9545	1	1	.29977
Exp.:6	Male	92(47.9)	92(47.9)	8(4.2)	(00)	1.5625	2	1(2)	.57546
	Female	52(59.1)	32(36.4)	4(4.5)	(00)	1.6818	2	1	.55802
Exp.:7	Male	66(34.4)	112(58.3)	14(7.3)	(00)	1.4896	2	2	.63071
	Female	26(29.5)	54(61.4)	8(9.1)	(00)	1.4773	2	2	.66050
Exp.:8	Male	164(85.4)	22(11.5)	6(3.1)	(00)	1.9167	1	1	.37365
	Female	58(65.9)	22(25)	8(9.1)	(00)	1.8409	1	1	.56500
Exp.:9	Male	154(80.2)	26(13.5)	12(6.2)	(00)	1.2604	1	1	.56503
	Female	54(61.4)	24(27.3)	10(11.4)	(00)	1.5000	1	1	.69481
Exp.:10	Male	68(35.4)	114(59.4)	10(5.2)	(00)	1.4583	1	2	.59521
	Female	38(43.2)	38(43.2)	12(13.6)	(00)	1.7045	2	1 (2)	.69744
Exp.:11	Male	110(57.3)	54(28.1)	28(14.6)	(00)	1.5729	1	1	.73427
	Female	46(52.3)	28(31.8)	14(15.9)	(00)	1.6364	1	1	.74559

Table 3: Statistical representation of the preferable expression in speech

- In the ninth set of expressions, similarity is noticed in both median and mode values. As per the mode values, both counterparts incline towards British expression.
- In the tenth set of expressions, similar mode but dissimilar median values are drawn. As per the mode values, equal number males inclined towards American and British expression whereas females prefer American expression.
- In the eleventh set of expressions, homogeneous median and mode values are elicited. As per the mode values, both counterparts prefer British expression.

As per the findings, preference for the use American and British expression among learners is equally distributed. In six cases, they prefer to use British expression and remaining five cases they like to use American. Once again, their

approach reflects that gender is not making any significant impact on the selection and use of the most appropriate variety of English.

Findings

In this study, gender has no explicit impact in the selection of the most preferred variety of English. On the basis of analysis and subsequent interpretation of the data, the following observations can be made:

- Males prefer to learn and use Indian English but females prefer to learn British or American variety of English and use Indian English. Duality in the perception and adoption is observed in females.
- At structural level, respondents have no significant difference in selection of the complete expressions. They preferred to use British expression in their communication in comparison to American expression. Comparatively the inclination towards American expression is slightly more in females than males.
- In writing, both male and female counterparts prefer to use British spelling in their written communication. Comparatively the inclination towards American spelling is slightly more in females than males.
- A mixed approach is observed with respect to the selection of expression in speech. Both American and British expressions are used by the respondents irrespective to their gender. Comparatively, British expressions are more preferred in comparison to American equivalents among the respondents.
- The first hypothesis that British English is the most famous and preferred variety of English among the tertiary level learners of English in the city of Lucknow, is validated in the findings.
- The second hypothesis is nullified. In most of the cases both males and females are inclined towards British English irrespective of their gender. Comparatively, the degree of inclination towards American English is slightly more in female.

This research is just an effort to develop an understanding of the impact of gender in use of English. This study is restricted to the learners of technical and professional education. Thus, making generalisation on the basis of responses by the learners of technical and professional courses may not have a wider acceptability.

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Appendix: Questionnaire cum evaluation sheet

Section: A

Name:

Course:

Institution:

Gender: Male ()

Female ()

Age:

I want to learn.....

Indian English ()

British English ()

American English ()

Not sure ()

Which variety of English do you prefer to use?

Indian English ()

British English ()

American English ()

Not sure ()

Section: B

<i>Select the most appropriate expression from each pair which you feel you use in your communication.</i>		
1	It's half past ten.	It's ten thirty.
2	We've just finished dinner.	We just finished dinner.
3	Who do you want to see?	Whom do you want to see?
4	She has already got up.	She has already gotten up.
5	Should I give you a pen?	Shall I give you a pen?

<i>Tick the expressions that you use in speech.</i>		
1	Cookie	Biscuit
2	Hood	Bonnet (on a car)
3	Boot (of a car)	Trunk
4	Lawyer	Solicitor
5	Counter-clockwise	Anti-clockwise
6	Area code	Dialling code
7	Diaper	Nappy
8	Bulletin board	Notice board
9	Chips	French-fries
10	Garbage	Rubbish
11	Ground floor	First floor

<i>Tick the expressions that you use in writing.</i>		
1	Centre	Center
2	Litre	Liter
3	Meter	Metre
4	Maneuver	Manoeuvre
5	Behaviour	Behavior
6	Favourite	Favorite
7	Color	Colour
8	Honour	Honor
9	Flavor	Flavour
10	Humor	Humour
11	Labor	Labour